

Business Workforce Planning in PT X to Support the Company Target Achievement

Rodrick M. K. Sitompul¹, Emilia Fitriana Dewi²

^{1,2} School of Business and Management, Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: Global business conditions and rupiah exchange rate fluctuations have also contributed to the oil and gas market decline since the outbreak of the novel coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic in Indonesia in the first quarter of 2020. In addition, the existing state of oil and gas, which generally experiences periodic declines, is a challenge for the company to maintain the company's business. Oil and gas companies, like other businesses, need people to carry out their activities and meet their production targets. The oil and gas business, by its very nature, requires sufficient human resources in terms of numbers and skills. If this is not regulated, it can lead to understaffing affecting goal achievement or over-employment, which can reduce company productivity. This study therefore aims to ensure adequate worker availability through workforce planning. Based on current personnel analysis and personnel planning strategy, PT. X has many flaws in its workforce planning/strategy, including its productivity, unstable headcount, lack of talent development and leadership skills. The strategic manpower framework for the internal labor market will be implemented by filling out the main activities excluded from internal resources and open core activities over the next five years from external recruitment to enhance the core functionality. It is proposed to set up a skills development program to improve technical and managerial skills to ensure the use of temporary workers and their readiness for current and future positions.

KEYWORDS: Competencies, Productivity, Workforce Strategy, Workforce Planning.

INTRODUCTION

When the oil and gas industry saw major disruptions, it was not only the emergence of the corona virus pandemic (Covid-19) that affected global crisis phenomena such as the economy and health in the first quarter of 2020, but also the oil price crash and international pressure to use non-fossil green energy has an impact on and the gas industry. In addition, the global business environment and rupiah exchange rate fluctuations have also contributed to the deterioration of the Indonesian oil and gas market. On the other hand, oil and gas field conditions, which are generally in a period of natural decline, pose another challenge for companies to stay in business. From the market demand side, the needs of the Indonesian people related to the use of energy from oil and gas raw materials are still large, exceeding the country's production capacity. As one of PT X, PT. X's oil and gas exploration and production subsidiaries play a key role in supplying raw materials for the final composition. Not only because one of the BUMN subsidiaries, namely PT. X, PT X also needs to generate profit for the company group and for the country as a contribution to the country.

Oil and gas companies, like other businesses, need people to conduct their operations and meet their targets. Referring to internal data, there is an opportunity for transportation and logistics work of Rp. 20.5 T which of course can be taken or worked on by PT X with adjustments to the company's core business, namely 3PL providers, but within the PT Pertamina group itself there are several companies that are almost the same business as PT X which are of course competitors in getting opportunities from jobs that there is. Currently, the marketing strategy carried out by PT X is still not good. This can be proven by the fact that there is no other income and only depends on the operations of the parent company. There is no specific marketing strategy that can directly attract customers outside of the parent company PT. Pertamina is one of the reasons for the lack of income other than the parent company. So far, PT X only does marketing to companies within PT. Pertamina itself and the brand owned by PT X is not very well known yet. Therefore, a marketing strategy is needed that can help PT X improve its brand as well as attract customers from outside the parent company to increase sales from PT X. The oil and gas business, by its very nature, requires sufficient human resources in terms of numbers and skills. Determining the right number and skills of employees needed, and the exact hours, was essential for an organization to manage its profits. If this is not regulated, it can lead to understaffing affecting goal achievement or overemployment, which can reduce company productivity. This requires workforce planning to ensure that the right people are available. This situation raises

the question of whether available talent can support the achievement of future goals. Based on the problem, organizations should evaluate their workforce plans to ensure that their workforce needs can best support business performance. The research questions for this study are the current condition of oil and gas X company based on SWOT assessment, workforce plans in place at oil and gas companies, and recommendations for workforce planning strategies in PT X to support the achievement of goals. For this reason, SWOT analysis and workforce planning becomes a necessity to ensure the best strategy for the company and availability of proper laborers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Workforce Planning

In the past, workforce planning was mainly called "personnel planning". The term is still occasionally used but has been phased out because it implies gender inequality and suggests a mechanical, quantitative approach to labor issues (Reilly, 1996). Manpower planning is the process by which a company attempts to anticipate the demand for labor and estimate the size, type, and sources of supply needed to meet those targets. (Reilly, 1996). Additionally, according to the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development Business (CIPD), workforce planning analyzes existing workforce, determines future labor requirements, and analyzes gaps between existing workforce and future needs, and handles implementation of organizational solutions. Workforce planning provides organizations with several benefits. This helps companies find the correct people in the correct place and time. This enables more effective and efficient use of the workforce and enables organizations to reorganize, reduce or expand their workforce (Sinclair, 2004).

The human resource planning process supports the organization by providing comprehensive goals that link various departments and gives employees space and time to think about shared future goals. (Sinclair, 2004). Workforce management is crucial and has many advantages, but most companies do not use systematic personnel planning. For example, only 22% of US companies have employee programs (Cotten, 2007).

Internal Labor Market

A human capital strategy is a clear understanding of both the current and future workforce. Like living things, the workforce is constantly evolving as new employees join, others retire or retire, and employees acquire new skills and experiences. Doeringer and Piore use the definition of the internal labor market to describe the practice of an organizational structure that avoids external labor. These practices reflect and foster a long-term commitment between employers and employees. For example, there are quite unique trends in traditional recruiting namely the trend towards hiring only the lower ranks in each recruitment path, and the practice of determining salary and compensation for work over a certain period of time. Strict workplace hierarchies rather than enhancing individual employee traits. At a higher level, ILM analysis provides key insights into how human capital systems work, reflecting actual practices and their outcomes. Therefore, it is possible to predict the impact of changes in management and market conditions. PSA analysis provides a platform to describe reality in determining human resources decisions. At the most basic level, it uses workforce data to look at the flow of people in and out of an organization to answer basic questions about an organization's workforce. Moreover, there are three types of ILM (Internal Labor Market) framework shapes namely pyramid, diamond, and block, as shown in Figure 1 (Mercer Human Resource Consulting LLC,2003).

Figure 1. Internal Labor Market Analysis Framework

A pyramidal organization is one that consists of highly hierarchical companies, with fewer people at the top and more people occupying each lower career level. A type of diamond-shaped tissue. Other companies whose workforce is more concentrated in the middle class are organizations that tend to have a more homogenous population, at least as far as employment is concerned. Finally, a block organizational type is one in which employees are distributed fairly evenly across levels. In this case, top management still has to be involved and focus on the core process, namely production.

Competency

Competence is an underlying characteristic of an individual that is causally associated with effective and/or superior performance in relation to criteria in tasks and situations (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). This concept originated with McClelland (1973), who used this approach to predict ability. This is very different from the intelligence tests that were widely used at the time. He argued that while intelligence influences performance, personal traits such as a person's motivation and self-image distinguish performance success from failure, and are found in multiple life roles, including professional roles. McClelland (1973) defined it as an underlying characteristic of successful performance. Spencer & Spencer (1993) describe five types of competency characteristics: motivations, traits, self-image, knowledge, and skills. There are two ways of thinking about the different interpretations of abilities. According to Dubois (2004), skill means knowledge or ability. In addition, the definition of skills is as a characteristic that supports an activity. This includes not only knowledge and skills, but also various traits such as motivation level and personality traits. Based on Boyatzis (2008), there is not a single factor, but a set of factors that distinguish successful and unsuccessful performances. These factors include personal qualities, motivations, experiences, and behavioral characteristics. Boyatzis defined competency as "the ability present in a person to lead to behavior consistent with the requirements of the job within the parameters of the organizational environment, which produces the desired outcome". He distinguished between threshold competence, which is the basic competence necessary to perform a job, and attainment competence, which distinguishes between high and low competence.

There are different types and levels of abilities, and they are categorized or organized in different ways. You can also subdivide them into organizations or individuals. Individual competency categories cover different competencies such as: Technical and personal characteristics. Some practitioners only categorize technical and non-technical competence. Technical competencies are specific to a particular role, non-technical competencies are more general. The function of competencies is attractive because it allows us to focus on factors that directly contribute to an organization's success (Raising the Bar, his HRM based on incompetence in 1996). Miller etc. (2001) state that there are two main reasons organizations use competencies. First, applying competencies to assessments, training, and other human resource processes can help improve employee performance. Second, competencies provide a means of articulating corporate values, translating the description of these values into HR practices, and individuals and organizations can understand these values. Another reason is using skills to achieve changes to the culture and improve the capabilities of the organization.

Cooper et al. (1998) pointed out some of the positive results achieved by valid and reliable competence-based management models. This includes making a direct connection between individual competencies and organizational strategies and goals. Create job or role profiles to match individuals to roles and responsibilities. Enables continuous monitoring and refinement of competency profiles. Facilitate employee selection and evaluation, training, and development. Helps hire individuals with unique skills that are costly and don't grow quickly. Helps organizations rank their competencies in both compensation and performance management.

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is one of the strategic planning frameworks used to assess an organization, plan, project or business activity. In addition, SWOT is also one of the important situational analysis methods that can help managers identify the internal and external conditions of the organization (environment). SWOT framework identify 2 point of views namely internal and external aspects. For internal views, the framework will analyze inside organizational factors such as organization strengths and weaknesses. While external views will analyze outside organization such as opportunities and threats from the environment. SWOT identifies internal and external aspects that are important to achieve business objectives. Internal aspects refer to features that are within the control of the business, while external aspects are factors beyond the control of the business (Bull et al., 2016). SWOT analysis can be used effectively to generate alternative choices for businesses. The technique can clearly explain how strengths and weaknesses can be matched with opportunities and threats.

SWOT analysis is a method that analyzes the condition of the company and involves four main components in two dimensions (internal and external) starting from strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Strengths and weaknesses are part of the internal conditions of the organization and/or company, while opportunities and threats are part of external factors. SWOT analysis is usually carried out in a grid of four quadrants. Table 2.1 below is an explanation of the four components in SWOT.

Table 1. SWOT Components

Component	Description
<i>Organizational Strengths</i>	Characteristics of companies that provide benefits to the company
Component	Description
<i>Organizational Weaknesses</i>	Characteristics of the company that shows the company's shortcomings
<i>Environmental Opportunities</i>	External elements that exist in the environment that provide benefits to the company
<i>Environmental Threats</i>	External elements that exist in the environment that can cause problems for the company

METHODOLOGY

This research uses framework evaluation research based on tasks and goals to be achieved. This research interviewed 6 participants and 5 of them at the management level. According to Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2015), at least three essential factors should be carefully considered when determining a study sample. These essential elements are the population, the target population, and the sample to be analyzed. This study identifies PT X stakeholders as a population. Targets managers. For this survey, the study got a sample from managers who deal with PT X employees. Primary data are collected from interviews via semi-structured interviews. Secondary data is collected from your organization's databases, your organization's website, and reports. The data was analyzed to map the existing state of the company's internal workforce and compare it to other oil and gas companies. All these analyses result in recommendations to support the achievement of corporate goals.

After that, external environmental conditions were identified using the Porter Five-Forces model and PEST analysis. In addition, internal environmental conditions are also identified using value chain analysis. Then after getting the internal and external environmental conditions at company, the next is the analysis of internal and external factors using the SWOT component. After obtaining internal and external factors from ABC, then a strategy is formulated using the SWOT matrix. Basically, all internal and external factor analysis is entered into the SWOT matrix and then formulates a strategy based on four combinations namely SO, ST, WO, and WT. The strategy that has been formulated based on the four combinations above, is then conducted in an FGD with the marketing strategy team to determine the best strategy and formulate future implementation plans for the company.

Scenario planning is illustrated as a method for training the future to avoid extreme events in decision making. Organizations typically create plans that contain different types of projections and projections. However, complications arise when organizations try to look for predictions well in advance. Organizations need management methods to uncover and explore the future business environment and identify potential risks and opportunities. Increased uncertainty requires multiple opportunities for preparation.

Scenario planning is a technique for dealing with uncertainty in future business operations. It is an effective medium- to longterm planning under uncertainty. Planning support strategize, plan for the unexpected, and focus on the right decision and direction (Lindgren & Bandhold, 2003). Scenario planning applies multiple possibilities while considering multiple uncertainties. Analysis also includes subjective interpretation. This method is especially useful in situations of uncertainty and volatility. In the past, poor strategic thinking has often resulted in costly surprises (Garvin & Levesque, 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Workforce Planning Process in X Company

Based on a document review and interviews regarding the personnel planning process at PT X, Human Resources Management was determined to be one of the HR roles at PT X. PT X believes that the key to success in human resource management is hiring the right employees with the necessary skills and attitudes that align with the company's values and culture. PT X develops a workforce management approach aligned with business objectives, competition environment, risk and human resource management risk. Figure 2 shows PTX's workforce planning strategy.

- a. Capability Gap. It means meeting competency needs for technical and managerial skills. Acquisition of technical skills through mapping
- b. Capacity Gap. To fill this gap, the company always prioritizes filling key positions, optimizing recruitment, recruiting new graduates and hiring experienced employees.
- c. Generation gap. To fill this gap, the company has built succession planning and coaching programs, rehired retired employees as coaches and mentors, and implemented knowledge management.

Figure 2. Workforce Planning Strategy

The Indonesian Statistics Center (BPS) will be carried out using a traditional recruitment (online) method through PT. Recruitment web of X with online psychological tests to enable more applicants to apply from anywhere in Indonesia. Subsequent processes such as user interviews and new management will take place with PT PT in Jakarta. Meanwhile, BPA and BKOPM are offered in the wealth sector depending on previous education required. Experienced employees are recruited based on their relevant experience and qualifications (relevant experience) for the position. Recruitment is done through a recruitment site that can bring in many candidates to apply from all regions in Indonesia. The test process carried out in recruitment usually takes place in Jakarta. A senior staff recruitment program is needed primarily to absorb/utilize manpower from the process of managing oil and gas blocks across his PT. X group. PTX runs an internship program to produce the best college graduates. This program is one of company strategies to meet the needs of temporary workers through emergency staffing. The internship strategy also support shape PTX's brand strategy. This enhances the image of the company and increases the interest of graduates to work for the company. Every two to three years, PTX conducts organizational reviews to assess the organization and align it with business goals. However, the process is not integrated and there are no workforce planning guidelines. Therefore, PTX must provide guidance or manuals to develop a comprehensive staffing plan that aligns staffing with the organization's strategic goals and crucial needs.

SWOT Analysis

In this section, the results of identifying the internal environment of PT. X used the value chain analysis method developed by Porter. The value chain concept involves all aspects of business activities and can be developed in combination with supply chains. While supply chains focus on the process of procuring goods and services from suppliers, value chains study added value at various intervals through a series of activities or processes aimed at creating profitable value for a product offering. In general, value chain business activities are usually divided into primary activities and secondary activities. The main activity is directly related to the creation of goods or services. Support activities are activities that help improve efficiency and bidding work to gain a stronger competitive advantage among co-workers. Based on the results of the assessment, the results of the internal environment identification analysis were as follows:

1. Good consistency of its product quality and good service reputation.
2. Good relationship and extensive network with suppliers
3. Lack of advertising programs
4. Lack of skills from marketing resources
5. Limited ability of internal funds to expand the business.

After that, the results of identifying the external environment of X Company using the PEST and Porter's Five-Forces analysis methods developed by Porter will be presented. Porter's 5 Forces is an analytical model used to help identify industry structures and help companies determine their competitive strategy and PEST stands for Political, Economic, Social and Technological. This analysis is used to assess these four external factors in relation to the business situation. Basically, PEST analysis helps determine how these factors will impact business performance and activities in the long term. This method is often used in combination with other business methods such as SWOT analysis and Porter's Five Forces to give a clear information of the situation and related internal and external factors.

This section will present the results of identifying the external environment which has been conducted through PEST analysis and Porter's Five-Forces. The following below is the result of the identification of the external environment that has been carried out.

1. The trend of the development of high demand from the logistics market
2. There is business and infrastructure assistance from the parent company.
3. Lack of business trust from the parent company
4. Intense rivalry among the existing competitors
5. High Threats of New Entrants

Identification results from the internal and external environment will be collected which will then be analyzed through Internal Key Factors (IFAS) and External Key Factors (EFAS) for X Company. After obtaining IFAS and EFAS from PT. X, then the results of data collection from the FGD with related stakeholders were collected and the weight, value and final score of each SWOT component were calculated. The value of this score will be the basis for determining the best strategy category to be used by the company based on the SWOT strategy coordinates. The following below is the result of calculating the score of eachSWOT component.

Table 2. IFAS Score Calculation

No.	Internal Factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Strengths				
1	Good consistency of product quality and good service reputation.	0.2	2.5	0.5
2	Good relationship and extensive network with suppliers	0.2	2.8	0.6
Sub Total				1.1

Weaknesses				
1	Lack of advertising strategies	0.2	3.42	0.7
2	Lack of skills from marketing employees	0.2	2.7	0.5
3	Limited ability of internal funds to expand the business	0.2	2.4	0.5
Sub Total				1.7
Final Score				2.8

Based on the table above, the sub-total value for the strength’s component is 1.1 and 1.7 for weaknesses. The higher the score of each component, the greater the influence of the component on company goals or it can be said that the strategy associated with this component is more necessary than the other components. In this case, a strategy to cover weaknesses is more needed than to strengthen the strengths component.

Table 3. EFAS Score Calculation

No.	External Factors	Weight	Rating	Skor
Opportunities				
1	The trend of the development of high demand from the logistics market	0.15	2.6	0.4
2	There is business and infrastructure assistance from the parent company	0.15	2.4	0.4
Sub Total				0.8
Threats				
1	Lack of business trust from the parent company	0.25	3.7	0.9
2	Intense competition among competitors	0.2	2.6	0.5
3	High threat of new entrants	0.25	2.66	0.7
Sub Total				2.1
Final Score				2.9

Meanwhile, based on the table above, the sub-total value for the Opportunities component is 0.8 and for Weaknesses is 2.1. The higher the score of each component, the greater the influence of the component on company goals or it can be said that the strategy associated with this component is more necessary than the other components. In this case, a strategy to anticipate threats is more needed than to take advantage of the opportunity’s component. The results of the previous SWOT component calculations are then mapped in a Cartesian diagram to determine the position of the company’s strategic needs.

Figure 3. SWOT Coordinate

Meanwhile, Figure 4.3 above is the result of mapping the Cartesian diagram according to the previously calculated coordinates. Based on the strategy mapping above, it is found that the Defense strategy category is prioritized compared to other combination strategies because it has the farthest distance from point 0. The meaning of this SWOT strategy mapping shows that strategies related to Defense are prioritized compared to other strategies. After obtaining the position from the company's SWOT, it is then followed by an FGD with stakeholders to discuss the strategies that will be used within the company. Based on the results above, a strategy in the Defense category (W-T combination) is more needed for companies to achieve goals and solve problems that occur. Therefore, the next process after the SWOT analysis is an FGD with stakeholders which will then formulate a strategy according to the company's needs. The following below is a strategy that was successfully formulated in the FGD.

Strategy	Program and Objectives	SWOT Component Coverage
Market Penetration	1. Advertising Goal: Increase brand awareness, increase sales	W1, W2, T1, T2, T3
	2. Sales Promotion Goal: Increase sales	W1, W2, T1, T2, T3
	3. Increase distribution coverage Goal: Increase sales and brand awareness	S1, O1, O2, O3

	4. Increased focus on Project Channels Goal: Increase brand awareness and image and increase sales	W1, W2, T1, T2, T3
	5. Approach Program Goals: Build a closer relationship with customers, Build positive value in word-of-mouth	S2, O1, O2
Product Development	1. Product Modification Goal: Attract new buyers and retain existing ones	S1, S2, T1, T2
	2. New Product Development Goal: Meet new customer needs	S1, S2, T1, T2, T3
Enter New Market Geography	1. Market expansion in other regions Goal: Increase sales and image	W1, W2, O1, O2
Development of Efficient Operations	1. Anticipate increased demand Goal: avoid inventory shortages and production and delivery	S1, S2, T2, T3
Strategy	Program and Objectives	SWOT Component Coverage
	delays	
	2. Efficient Operation Goal: Reduce costs and increase profits	S1, S2, T2, T3
Develop good HRM practices	1. Revitalizing the Role of the HR department Objective: Develop a good HRM practice with a strategic orientation	W1, W2, T1, T2, T3

After obtaining the formulation of the strategy and its implementation, it is necessary to have strategic priorities that need to be carried out by the company's stakeholders. The priority strategy that can be used by stakeholders is through a SWOT analysis that has been done before. It can be seen that the combination strategy needed for the company is a defense strategy, namely a combination of Weaknesses and Threats. Therefore, the priority strategies to be used within the company are as follows: (1) Advertising;(2) Sales Promotion; (3) Increased focus on the project channel; (4) Revitalizing the Role of the HR Department. These

strategies then aim to increase brand awareness and company image to increase sales and increase market share that can be provided by the company. After that, the research focused on revitalizaing the role of the HR department and develop good HRM practices through workforce strategy and planning for X company.

Scenario Planning

Applying scenario planning to business operations makes a sustainable long-term business strategy to make strategic decisions under uncertainty. Constant innovation in organizational development enables flexible and creative thinking, aligning key stakeholders with a shared vision. Scenario planning is used in workforce planning to see how different futures affect the demands placed on employees to meet their needs and how easily those demands can be met. can be shown. Staffing plans can be tested against different scenarios to determine where staffing decisions need to change in response to an incident (CIPD, 2018).

Figure 4. Scenario Planning Process

PT X is one of state-owned oil and gas company and one of the contractors of oil and gas SKK, which manages the business. PT X's business operations are easily influenced by stakeholder guidelines regarding the direction of the company especially by the government. Political and governmental regulation of oil and gas (fossil energy) extraction is therefore an important source of uncertainty. Another key source of uncertainty is the alternative prices of green energy, which is now emerging as an energy source of choice. From the top two scenario with the most critical uncertainties, combined into a 2x2 matrix, four scenarios are obtained in the quadrants:

Figure 5. Scenario Planning Framework

The workforce planning scenario and the options that have been formulated in the previous section are expected to provide results that are in accordance with real conditions. In this section, the expected results to be provided from the implementation of scenarios and options will be explained in the following table.

Table 4. Workforce Planning Analysis

Quadrant	Expected Results and Analysis
Quadrant 1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The workforce needed is increasingly difficult to obtain because of the high competence and skills required. 2. Expectations on the number of workers will continue to decline with the company's high focus on the efficiency of business processes 3. The result of implementing this option depends on the training program for employees. If the company does not provide the right training program with the needs of real conditions, it will be difficult to compete with competitors. 4. Low prices make companies have to reduce their costs where one of these costs is labor so that the workforce remains reduced.
Quadrant 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The workforce needed is increasingly difficult to obtain because of the high competence and skills required. 2. The number of workers is increasing because new production sites will be expanded to increase production and sales. 3. The result of implementing this option depends on the training program for employees. If the company does not provide the right training program with the needs of real conditions, it will be difficult to compete with competitors.
Quadrant 3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Expectations on the number of workers will continue to decline with the company's high focus on the efficiency of business processes 2. The search for workers for companies has become easier due to business diversification so that they are not too focused on oil and gas skills 3. The number of workers is going to be unstable due to business diversification and the uncertainty of the company's business
Quadrant	Expected Results and Analysis
Quadrant 4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Expectations on the number of workers will continue to decline with the company's high focus on the efficiency of business processes. 2. The search for workers for companies has become easier due to business diversification so that they are not too focused on oil and gas skills

CONCLUSIONS

Based on current personnel analysis, PT. X needs a way to manage its workforce plans for a sustainable, long-term corporate strategy. Applying scenario planning to business problems creates a sustainable long-term corporate strategy for making strategic decisions under uncertainty. After evaluation and planning in this study, we have the following recommendations: This can be considered by the company (1) Separating administrative duties from the strategic and tactical tasks of support functions and implementing the Shared Service Center (SSC) concept in PT. X (2) Realize the concept of the internal labor market strategy by filling important posts that will be vacant in the next five years, especially managerial and managerial positions, with internal resources (3) Develop core functions by filling vacant cores Strengthening positions by filling selective positions Strengthening technical and managerial skills to ensure readiness for current and future positions through the use of lower level positions and temporary staff through external recruitment It is proposed to establish a skills development program for The program consists of an onsite approach and an offsite approach. in technology development programs. In short, it is a professional development program whose focus is on professional training, placement, and rotation. In leadership development programs, i. H. In the Leadership Development Programme, the focus of the program is on leadership coaching and mentoring.

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